

Validation of an Assessment of Chromogenic Media Against Conventional Culture Techniques for Isolation, Identification, and Direct Antibiotic Susceptibility Testing of Uropathogens in Resource-Poor Settings

Kalpesh Khutade*¹, Harshada Shah², Samiksha Patil³, Hiren Patel⁴

¹⁻⁴Department of Microbiology, Vedantaa Institute of Medical Sciences, Vedantaa Hospital and Research Centre, Palghar, Maharashtra, MUHS University, India -401606

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*Corresponding Author Email: kalpeshkhutade111@gmail.com

Abstract

The study was planned to evaluate chromogenic media against conventional techniques in terms of correct identification, ease of reporting, and reduction in cost. This cross-sectional prospective analytical study was carried out from January 1, 2022, to September 30, 2023, at Vedantaa Institute of Medical Sciences, Palghar. Urine samples were inoculated on MacConkey agar, blood agar, CLED agar, and chromogenic media simultaneously and incubated overnight. Imparting a distinct color to the isolated bacterial colony was visualized and identified by Hichrome UTI agar. Direct susceptibility testing by disc diffusion on clinical samples offers a rapid and inexpensive method of obtaining information to guide antimicrobial therapy. A total of 531 samples were culture-positive clinical isolates. Significant growth was obtained in 531 (100%) plates of HiCrome UTI, followed by CLED agar 521 (98.11%), Blood agar 511 (96.23%), and MacConkey agar 497 (93.59%). The sensitivity patterns of *S. aureus* to the following antibiotics: gentamicin, tetracycline, penicillin, and levofloxacin were 12 (85.71%), 11 (78.57%), 9 (64.28%), and 7 (7.00%), respectively. The sensitivity patterns of *Pseudomonas* spp. to the following antibiotics: piperacillin-tazobactam, amikacin, ceftazidime-avibactam, and gentamicin were 62 (87.32%), 43 (60.56%), 35 (49.29%), and 21 (29.57%). *Enterococcus* spp. was sensitive to Penicillin 79 (94.94%), Ampicillin 68 (80.95%), Vancomycin 57 (67.85%), and Tetracycline 46 (54.76%). Enterobacteriaceae showed high sensitivity to Meropenem (84.25%), Ceftazidime (67.68%), Piperacillin-Tazobactam (55.80%), and Ampicillin-Sulbactam (41.44%). Concluded that the Hichrome agar medium can be a desirable, simple primary isolation and identification medium that significantly lessens the daily workload associated with urine culture in microbiology laboratories.

Keywords

Bacterial growth, CLED agar, Conventional culture system, Hi Chrome UTI agar, Urinary tract infection

INTRODUCTION

Urinary tract infections (UTIs) are among the most common bacterial infections worldwide, affecting all age groups in community and hospital settings (Ali *et al.*, 2023; Harris and Fasolino, 2022). They represent 10–20% of all infections treated in primary care and 30–40% of infections treated in hospitals (Nahar *et al.*, 2020). It is common in females due to the short urethra, and about 60% of women are reported to have experienced the UTI once in their lifetime. The increasing risk factor in females is due to short urethra, pregnancy, and the absence of prostatic secretions, which easy contamination of the urinary tract. 90% of pregnant women develop urethral dilation and are susceptible to UTIs. In the need to confirm the diagnosis and manage the patient, a microbiological diagnosis is a must (Jain *et al.*, 2023; Bajoria *et al.*, 2019).

Urine samples constitute a large share of the daily workload of microbiological laboratories (Stefaniuk, 2018). For many years, blood agar, CLED agar (cystine-lactose-electrolyte-deficient agar), and MacConkey agars have been used for the detection of urinary tract pathogens as well as for differentiation. These current detection methods are time-consuming and require at least 24 hours for a negative culture and up to three days for susceptibility data if positive cultures are discovered (Jadhav *et al.*, 2016; Bouslah *et al.*, 2020).

The problem of urine culture has been addressed by the introduction of chromogenic agar medium, which is commercially available. CA medium is increasingly being used as a versatile tool in the early differentiation and identification of bacterial isolates from clinical specimens (Sachu and Samuel, 2022). Chromogenic Media: chromogenic substrates are specifically broken down by the enzyme possessed by the particular bacteria, thus imparting a distinct color to the isolated bacterial colony, which can be visualized and identified. Chromogenic media have shown advantages, which include a 20% reduction in time for identification, a reduction in workload, easier recognition of mixed growth, and a reduction in the number of biochemical tests performed for the identification of bacteria, which ultimately results in cost reduction (Khalid *et al.*, 2021; Akter *et al.*, 2014). The present study was undertaken to evaluate and compare the effectiveness of conventional culture systems and chromogenic agar medium for the isolation, identification, and direct testing of uropathogens' antibiotic susceptibility. Which will help reduce the cost in resource-poor settings.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study comprised 1289 clinically suspected acute UTI patients of all ages and gender. This study was

undertaken at the Vedantaa Institute of Medical Sciences, Vedantaa Hospital and Research Centre, Dahanu, Palghar, situated in a rural setting. The study was carried out to compare the utility of the conventional method with HiCrome UTI Medium for the detection of uropathogens. It was conducted between 1 January 2022 and 30 September 2023 (Jain *et al.*, 2023).

All clinically suspected cases of urinary tract infections admitted to this hospital were included in the study. Either clean mid-stream urine samples or from the sampling port of an indwelling catheter with a sterile syringe and needle were collected. Criteria of inclusion for those indoor patients with UTI were the following: a temperature greater than 38°C, the presence of plenty of pus cells or a high-power field in urine samples, >10⁵ colony-forming units per ml of uncentrifuged urine (Bose, 2015).

The urine samples were inoculated on MacConkey's agar, Blood agar and CLED agar (cystine-lactose-electrolyte-deficient agar). The inoculated plates were incubated aerobically at 37°C for 24 hours. In the conventional method, *Enterobacteriaceae* isolates were identified by the following biochemical tests: motility, indole production, nitrate reduction, glucose fermentation with or without gas production, hydrogen sulfide production, urea hydrolysis, lysine and ornithine decarboxylation, and sodium citrate utilization. Gram-negative microorganisms other than *Enterobacteriaceae* were identified by colony morphology, pigment production, gelatin, and the catalase test. The oxidase test was performed for non-fermenters. *Staphylococcus aureus* and coagulase-negative *Staphylococci* were identified by Gram staining, catalase, and coagulase tests, and novobiocin susceptibility (Ali *et al.*, 2023). *Streptococci* were identified up to species level by PYR test, the bacitracin sensitivity test, the bile solubility test, and the aesculin hydrolysis test. All the media and biochemicals were procured from Hi Media Laboratories, India.

For the isolation and identification of uropathogens using HiCrome UTI Medium. The urine samples were inoculated on chromogenic UTI agar. The inoculated plates were incubated aerobically at 37°C for 24 hours. The gold standard of this method was the absence of biochemical tests for the identification of isolates.

All urine samples that were received in the lab underwent direct susceptibility testing right away. An unadjusted, well-mixed urine sample was used to test for confluence on a HiChrome agar plate using a sterile cotton swab. The extra fluid was then expelled. Using sterile forceps, commercial antimicrobial discs were firmly placed on the agar surface after being distributed via a multidisc

dispenser. Following incubation at 35°C for 16 to 18 hours, plates were read the following day. According to the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI), zone diameter was measured and interpreted. In accordance with CLSI standards, the antimicrobial susceptibilities of isolates from pure cultures were evaluated for comparison using a conventional disc diffusion method.

Control strains used for the study were the following:
Color of the colony.

Enterococcus faecalis ATCC 29212: blue, small

Escherichia coli ATCC 25922: pink purple

Klebsiella pneumoniae ATCC 13883, blue purple

Pseudomonas aeruginosa ATCC 27853: colorless (greenish pigment may be observed)

Proteus mirabilis ATCC 12453, light brown

Staphylococcus aureus subsp. aureus ATCC 25923: golden yellow

Statistical analysis: The data was anonymized and presented in percentages and graphs.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A total of 531 patients of different age and sex suffering from UTI were included in this study. Among the patients, 215 (40.48%) were male and 316

(59.51%) were female. Their age distribution showed that 335/531 (63.08%) patients were in the age group 01 to 40 years, followed by 196/531 (36.91%) in the age group 41 to above 70 years. Majority of the UTI patients 435/531 (81.90%) were in the 20-50 years age group followed by >50 years 40 (7.53%) and below 20 years 56(10.54%). Regarding rate of bacterial growth, slightly higher number of culture positive cases was noted among female 316/531 (59.51%) than male 215/531 (40.48%) Fig. (1). This was in correlation with the study conducted by Moyo *et al.*, (2010), in which the isolation of pathogens from females was at a rate of 54.4% and from males was at a rate of 45.6%. Another study by Nehar *et al.*, (2020) also showed that among the patients, 121 (40.33%) were male and 179 (59.67%) were female, with a male-female ratio of 1:1.48. Anatomic factors like the short urethra, hormonal factors, and pregnancy contribute to the female preponderance of the UTI s. Our study demonstrated that the highest incidence of urinary isolates was in the 20–50 (81.90%)-year-old age group. This is coincident with the study by Shafiyabi *et al.*, (2014). In this study, a peak incidence of UTI was noted in the age group between 21 and 50 years (55%).

Fig. 1. Culture positive cases detected in chromogenic agar medium in relation to the age and gender of the patients (N=531)

Table 1. Spectrum of organisms isolated from culture positive cases (n=531)

Organism	Total isolates	Percentage (%)
<i>E. coli</i>	258	48.59
<i>Klebsiella</i> spp.	92	17.33
<i>Enterococcus</i> spp.	84	15.82
<i>Pseudomonas</i> spp.	71	13.37
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	14	2.64
<i>Acinetobacter</i> spp.	9	1.69
<i>Proteus</i> spp.	3	0.56
Total	531	100.00

Table 2. Evaluation of four culture media for the rate of isolation of uropathogens (n=531)

Bacteria	Total isolates (n)	HiCrome UTI Agar (%)	CLED agar (%)	Blood Agar (%)	MacConkey agar (%)
E. coli	258	258 (100%)	258 (100%)	258 (100%)	258 (100%)
Klebsiella spp.	92	92 (100%)	92 (100%)	92 (100%)	92 (100%)
Enterococcus spp.	84	84 (100%)	84 (100%)	76 (100%)	76 (90.47%)
Pseudomonas spp.	71	71 (100%)	71 (100%)	71 (100%)	71 (100%)
Staphylococcus aureus	14	14 (100%)	14(100%)	14 (100%)	00 (00%)
Acinetobacter spp.	9	9 (22.22%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
Proteus spp.	3	3 (100%)	2 (66.66%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
Total	531	531 (100%)	521 (98.11%)	511 (96.23%)	497 (93.59%)

Table 3. Rate of matching of bacterial isolates on HiCrome UTI agar medium with the standard colony color (N=531)

Bacteria	Total isolates (n)	Matched (%)	Not matched (%)
E. coli	258	255 (98.83%)	3 (1.16%)
Klebsiella spp.	92	92 (100%)	0 (0%)
Enterococcus spp.	84	84 (100%)	0 (0%)
Pseudomonas spp.	71	71 (100%)	0 (0%)
Staphylococcus aureus	14	14 (100%)	0 (0%)
Acinetobacter spp.	9	9 (100%)	0 (0%)
Proteus spp.	3	3 (100%)	0 (0%)
Total	531	528 (99.43%)	3 (0.56%)

Table 4. Antimicrobial susceptibility rate found in Staphylococcus aureus, Pseudomonas spp., Enterococcus spp. and total Enterobacteriaceae (n= 531)

Staphylococcus (n=14)	aureus	Pseudomonas spp. (n= 71)	Enterococcus spp. (n = 84)	Total Enterobacteriaceae (n= 362)			
Antibiotics	Sensitivity	Antibiotics	Sensitivity	Antibiotics	Sensitivity		
Azithromycin	2 (14.28%)	Ceftazidime	19 (26.76%)	Ampicillin	68 (80.95%)	Ampicillin	102 (28.18%)
Clarithromycin	3 (21.42%)	Gentamicin	21 (29.57%)	Penicillin	79 (94.94%)	Cefazolin	78 (21.55%)
Clindamycin	5 (35.71%)	Tobramycin	2 (2.81%)	Linezolid	21 (25%)	Gentamicin	105 (29.01%)
Cefoxitin	1 (7.14%)	Piperacillin-tazobactam	62 (87.32%)	Teicoplanin	31 (36.90%)	Tobramycin	43 (11.88%)
Penicillin	9 (64.28%)	Amikacin	43 (60.56%)	Vancomycin	57 (67.85%)	Amikacin	77 (21.27%)
Trimethoprim-Sulfamethoxazole	4 (28.57%)	Aztreonam	21 (29.57%)	Gentamicin (High-level resistance testing only)	39 (46.42%)	Amoxicillin-clavulanate	23 (6.35%)
Ceftaroline	2 (14.28%)	Cefepime	11 (15.49%)	Streptomycin (High-level resistance testing only)	23 (27.38%)	Ampicillin-sulbactam	150 (41.44%)
Linezolid	2 (14.28%)	Ceftazidime-avibactam	35 (49.29%)	Levofloxacin	12 (14.28%)	Azithromycin	56 (15.47%)
Tetracycline	11 (78.57%)	Levofloxacin	16 (22.53%)	Fosfomycin	21 (25%)	Cefepime	60 (16.57%)
Levofloxacin	7 (7.00%)	Meropenem	13 (18.30%)	Nitrofurantoin	14 (16.66%)	Cefotaxime	34 (9.39%)
Gentamicin	12 (85.71%)			Tetracycline	46 (54.76%)	Cefotetan	46 (12.71%)
Minocycline	3 (21.42%)					Ceftazidime-avibactam	24 (6.63%)
Nitrofurantoin	2 (14.28%)					Ceftriaxone	7 (1.93%)
Sulfisoxazole	1 (7.14%)					Cefuroxime	86 (23.76%)

Trimethoprim 1 (7.14%)

Meropenem	305 (84.25%)
Piperacillin–	202 (55.80%)
Tazobactam	
Aztreonam	23 (6.35%)
Ceftazidime	245 (67.68%)
Ceftaroline	89 (24.59%)
Tetracycline	24 (6.63%)
Cefazolin	56 (15.47%)
Fosfomycin	34 (9.41%)
Nitrofuranto	32 (8.84%)
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Out of 531 isolates, *E. coli* was the leading bacteria 258 (48.59%) followed by *Klebsiella spp.* 92 (17.33%), *Enterococcus spp.* 84 (15.82%), *Pseudomonas spp.* 71 (13.37%), *Staphylococcus aureus* 14 (02.64%), *Acinetobacter spp.* 09 (01.69%) and *Proteus spp.* 03(0.56%) Table (1). A similar pattern and rate of isolation of uropathogens were also observed by Nehar *et al.*, (2020). Another study by Jadhav *et al.*, (2016); Karah *et al.*, (2020) showed that among all the bacterial isolates (n = 578), *E. coli* had the highest number (195), followed by *Klebsiella spp.*, which was found in a total of 81 samples, and *Staphylococcus aureus*, which constitutes 12.97% of the total urinary isolates, respectively. This is in accordance with a study carried out by Akter *et al.*, (2014), which showed patterns of bacterial isolates from urine culture. *E. coli* was the leading bacteria isolated from 118 (59.30%) samples, followed by *Klebsiella spp.* 38 (19.09%), *Enterococcus spp.* 23 (11.56%), *Pseudomonas spp.* 04 (2.01%), and *Proteus spp.* 03 (1.51%). These urinary isolates were presumptively identified on Hicrome UTI agar, CLED agar, Blood, and MacConkey agar. The evaluation results of four culture media for the rate of isolation of uropathogens are shown in Table Table (2), maximum number of isolates was presumptively identified on Hicrome UTI agar (100%) and the rate of presumptively identification from CLED agar 521 (98.11%), Blood agar 511 (96.23%) and MacConkey agar 497 (93.59%). The studies carried out by Jain *et al.* (2023) showed chromosomal agar (CA) supported the growth of all isolates grown on blood agar (BA), whereas Mac Conkey supported only 93% of growth. In another study by Nehar *et al.*, (2020), it was seen that both HiCrome UTI agar supported 100% bacterial growth, while MAC agar yielded 133 (91.72%) bacterial growth out of 145 total isolates.

The rate of matching with the standard colour for bacterial isolates on HiCrome UTI agar medium is shown in Table (3). It is evident that the colony colour of all isolates of *Klebsiella spp.*, *Enterococcus*

spp., *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Acinetobacter spp.* and *Proteus spp.* matched 100% with the standard colony colour on HiCrome UTI agar medium. While, out of 258 isolates of *E. coli*, 03 (01.16 %) did not match with the standard colony colour because of absence of β – galactosidase activity in that strain by Bose, (2015). According to Sharmin *et al.*, (2010), the high prevalence of *E. coli* in UTI cases may be due to its existence as a normal flora in the large intestine and colonization in the perineal area. However, HiCrome UTI agar failed to produce expected colony colors for 3 (03.33%) of the *E. coli*. This behavior of certain bacterial species on chromogenic agar media has also been reported by other investigators (Nehar *et al.*, 2020).

Table 4 shows the antimicrobial susceptibility rate found in *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas spp.*, *Enterococcus spp.*, and total Enterobacteriaceae. The sensitivity patterns of *S. aureus* to the following antibiotics: gentamicin, tetracycline, penicillin, and levofloxacin were 12 (85.71%), 11 (78.57%), 9 (64.28%), and 7 (7.00%), respectively. Gentamicin, Amoxycillin/clavulanate, Streptomycin, Cloxacillin, Erythromycin, Chloramphenicol, Cotrimoxazole, Tetracycline, Penicillin, Ciprofloxacin, Ofloxacin, Levofloxacin, Ceftriaxone, Amoxycillin, and vancomycin have been reported with sensitivity patterns of 92.4%, 63.0%, 44.2%, 35.8%, 52.4%, 61.9%, 15.5%, and 31.2%, according to Onwubiko *et al.* (2011). The sensitivity patterns of *Pseudomonas spp.* to the following antibiotics: piperacillin-tazobactam, amikacin, ceftazidime-avibactam, and gentamicin were 62 (87.32%), 43 (60.56%), 35 (49.29%), and 21 (29.57%), respectively. Javiya *et al.* (2008) studied combination drugs like ticarcillin + clavulanic acid, piperacillin + tazobactam, cefoperazone + sulbactam, cefotaxime + sulbactam, ceftriaxome + sulbactam, and monotherapy with amikacin, which showed higher sensitivity to *Pseudomonas* infections. *Enterococcus spp.* was sensitive to Penicillin 79 (94.94%), Ampicillin 68 (80.95%), Vancomycin 57 (67.85%), and Tetracycline 46

(54.76%). Similar study by Kraszewska et al. (2022). Enterobacteriaceae showed high sensitivity to Meropenem (84.25%), Ceftazidime (67.68%), Piperacillin-Tazobactam (55.80%), and Ampicillin-Sulbactam (41.44%), like those studied by Mulla et al. (2011).

CONCLUSION

Advanced diagnostic tools, like molecular methods, might not be affordable to all and need technical skills to perform. The overall findings of our study suggest that HiCrome UTI Medium supports the growth of all uropathogens. Furthermore, it provided the correct and rapid identification of organisms based on their color morphology. Therefore, it should be incorporated into routine laboratory work to process urinary cultures. DST using HiCrome media helps with the concurrent confirmation of bacterial species. It may be suggested for use as the main urine culture medium by clinical microbiology laboratories. The use of HiCrome UTI Medium minimizes the workload of a laboratory and helps treating clinicians initiate treatment with the right drug and dose at the right time for the right patient.

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